

THE PROBLEM OF DEATH AND IMMORTALITY IN THE POETRY OF VASYL STUS

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Abstract

The article is the first to explore the philosophical problem of death and immortality in the poems of Vasyl Stus, a Ukrainian hero and fighter against the totalitarian Soviet regime.

The author comes to the conclusion that V. Stus is a man of meta-boundary existence in the terminology of the Kyiv philosopher Nazip Khamitov. The creative heritage of V. Stus indicates that he is a person with a well-formed worldview. V. Stus is a patriot of Ukraine who is ready to die for the love of his Fatherland.

Vasyl Stus is a warrior of freedom and a symbol of the problem of death and immortality of the personality of every Ukrainian who fights for the independence of his Ukrainian people.

Keywords: death, immortality, personality, V. Stus, V. Kipiani.

Formulation of the problem. The Russian-Ukrainian war brought up not only the problem of death and immortality with all its sharpness. Russian aggression against the peaceful people of Ukraine made the philosophical study of the biography and poetry of V. Stus relevant.

Vasyl Stus is the embodiment, on the one hand, of the martyr of the Ukrainian people who suffered from the then totalitarian Soviet government. On the other hand, he is one of the geniuses of Ukrainian literature and the embodiment of the Ukrainian spirit of indomitability and freedom.

The creative path and genius of Stus are understudied in Ukrainian philosophy and require more in-depth analysis and understanding. After all, the figure of Vasyl Stus embodies the problem of death and immortality of the human personality, which opposes Russian barbarism and the totalitarianism of the Bolsheviks.

The aim of the article is to investigate the problem of death and immortality in the poetry of V. Stus.

Presenting main material. According to the Encyclopedia of the History of Ukraine, Vasyl Semenovich Stus is a “poet, literary critic, publicist, human rights defender” [1].

We would like to supplement this definition. Vasyl Semenovich Stus is a Ukrainian philosopher who wrote in the field of philosophical art (N. Khamitov) [5].

In his poetry, V. Stus raised the issue of death and immortality. Thus, in the poem “How good it is that I am not afraid of death,” the poet and philosopher Stus writes:

“How good it is that I am not afraid of death
and I do not ask if my cross is heavy.
Oh my God, I don't stoop low
in anticipation of unknown layers.
Who lived-loved and did not accumulate filth,
hatred, curse, remorse.
My people, I will return to you
and in death I will turn to life
with his suffering and not angry face,
as a son, I will bow down to you
and honestly look into your honest eyes,
and I will shed honest tears.

I want to live like this for even an hour,
when my trouble will be over.

Let Lesya Ukrainka come to visit
Franko, Shevchenko and Skovoroda” [4].

So, on the one hand, we see that despite the tragic circumstances of his life, because V. Stus was a slave of the Soviet regime and sat in exile in captivity, he shows a desire for life, he wants to live, and on the other hand, he shows fearlessness before death and says that he is not afraid to die, because the truth is with Stus, and this truth gives him hope for immortality.

Death surrounds V. Stus in prison, it does not leave the poet. He writes:

“Deadly alcohol in prison evenings,
of prison dawns, blind as a twin, mercury.

And a hundred dead men are waiting with their
hearts filled

of my death, but of my fate.

And day after day the fools chew,
to sprinkle the soul with something.

Smoke is billowing – the days are crazy
finish or start the journey –

according to the memories that nestle in the
memory,

for the losses that you have done to the best
of your abilities up rush when God acted
like a fierce scourge and a strongman” [3].

Therefore, V. Stus believes that the causes of death lie in metaphysical reality. According to Stus, death equalizes all people before God [3].

Reflecting on the causes of V. Stus' death, Ukrainian researcher V. Kipiani asks: “Heart, suicide or murder? How Vasyl Stus died” [2].

According to V. Kipiani, “on the night of September 4, 1985, the 47-year-old poet and human rights activist Vasyl Stus passed away in the cell of the special regime camp VS-389/36 in the village of Kuchino, Chusovsky district, Perm region. There are several versions of why this happened” [2, p. 617].

The actual cause of Stus' death is not known for sure. V. Kipiani is inclined to the fact that Stus died, on the one hand, due to starvation in prison, and on the other, due to heart problems.

Conclusions. So, we can come to the conclusion that Vasyl Stus is a person of meta-boundary existence

(in the terminology of meta-anthropology of the Ukrainian philosopher N. Khamitov). After all, his poetry and creative path testify to the fact that he is a person with a formed worldview. For the sake of his patriotic ideals and love for Ukraine, Vasyl Stus is ready to die.

V. Stus is a freedom fighter, he is the embodiment and symbol of the problem of death and immortality of the personality of every Ukrainian who fights for the independence of the Ukrainian people.

We are convinced that all conscious Ukrainians should read the poetry of V. Stus, because it has a philosophical and anthropological content and fills its readers with love for Ukraine.

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